

PECHMANN'S CONDENSATION OF METHYL β -RESORCYLATE WITH ETHYL α -ALKYLACETOACETATES.

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Methyl β -resorcylicate has been condensed with ethyl α -methyl-, α -ethyl-, α -propyl-, α -butyl-, and α -benzyl acetoacetates in the presence of sulphuric acid. In each case the condensation product is a mixture of 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid and its methyl ester.

In continuation of the previous work (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 717) we have successfully condensed methyl β -resorcylicate with ethyl α -methyl-, α -ethyl-, α -propyl-, α -butyl-, and α -benzylacetoacetates. In each case the condensation product is a mixture of 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid and its methyl ester (I, R=H or Me respectively and X = CH₃, C₂H₅, C₃H₇, C₄H₉ and CH₂.C₆H₅ respectively). The constitution of all the condensation products has been established by decarboxylating the acids by heating in sealed tube with water. The decarboxylated products are directly compared with specimens of 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methylcoumarins (II, X=CH₃, C₂H₅, C₃H₇, C₄H₉ or CH₂.C₆H₅ respectively) prepared from resorcinol and ethyl α -alkylacetoacetates. Attempts to condense β -resorcylic acid itself with ethyl α -methylacetoacetate were unsuccessful.

The inhibiting effect of the 4-carbomethoxy group in the resorcinol nucleus on the coumarin condensation is thus found to be less than that of the 4-nitro group, as 4-nitroresorcinol has been found to condense only with ethyl acetoacetate and no product could be isolated by reacting 4-nitroresorcinol with ethyl α -methyl- or α -ethylacetoacetates (Chakravarti and Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 37).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Purification of Materials.—Ethyl α -ethyl-, α -propyl-, and α -butyl-acetoacetates obtained from Dr. Theodor Schüchardt were found to contain ethyl acetoacetate in appreciable quantity. Ethyl α -butylacetoacetate was purified by distillation under reduced pressure but ethyl α -ethyl- and ethyl α -propyl-

acetoacetates could not be thus purified. When unpurified ethyl α -ethylacetoacetate was condensed with methyl β -resorcyate, the product obtained gave a melting point range of about 30° . On purification by crystallisation it gave methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate. The impure ethyl α -ethylacetoacetate was purified by washing repeatedly with 3% sodium hydroxide and then distilled when almost all the ethyl acetoacetate was removed. Ethyl α -propylacetoacetate could not be completely purified by this treatment and on condensation with methyl β -resorcyate it gave a product, melting indefinitely with a long range, which could not be purified by further crystallisation. The acetyl derivative, however, came out pure and the pure coumarin ester (I, R=Me; X=C₃H₇) was obtained from this by hydrolysis.

All the coumarin esters and acids gave an intense violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and a strong blue fluorescence with alkali.

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (I, R=Me; X=Me).—Sulphuric acid (80%; 60 c.c.) was added gradually with shaking to a mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (15 g.) and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (14 g.). After keeping for 40 hours at room temperature the reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice. The product obtained was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The insoluble solid was filtered, and the filtrate acidified, when the free acid was precipitated as a granular solid. The coumarin ester crystallised from rectified spirit in shining needles, m.p. $212-113^\circ$, yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 4.8. C₁₃H₁₄O₅ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.8 per cent).

It is sparingly soluble in 10% caustic soda solution, rectified spirit, methyl alcohol and petroleum ether and more soluble in benzene, chloroform, acetone and glacial acetic acid.

The acetyl derivative, prepared by refluxing the ester (0.5 g.) for 3 hours with acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) and 4-5 drops of pyridine, crystallised from dilute alcohol in short shining needles, m.p. $178-80^\circ$. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 4.8. C₁₅H₁₄O₆ requires C, 62.2; H, 4.8 per cent).

The benzoyl derivative, prepared by heating the ester (0.5 g.), dissolved in pyridine, with benzoyl chloride (1.5 c.c.) for 2 hours on a boiling water-bath, crystallised from rectified spirit in long shining needles, m.p. $159-60^\circ$. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 4.6. C₂₀H₁₆O₆ requires C, 68.2; H, 4.5 per cent).

The methyl ether, prepared by refluxing the ester (0.5 g.), dissolved in acetone (50 c.c.) for 20 hours with fused potassium carbonate (1 g.) and methyl iodide (3 c.c.), was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. $185-87^\circ$. (Found: C, 63.7; H, 5.3. C₁₄H₁₄O₅ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (I, R=H and X=Me), obtained by the acidification of sodium bicarbonate solution, as mentioned above, was crystallised from rectified spirit in pointed needles, m.p. 263°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 57.7; H, 4.7. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$, $1H_2O$ requires C, 57.2; H, 4.8 per cent). The same acid was also obtained by the hydrolysis of the coumarin ester by cold alkali. The ester (0.5 g.) was shaken up with sodium hydroxide (10%, 20 c.c.) and kept for 48 hours when it went completely into solution. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from rectified spirit in shining needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with acid obtained from above was 263°, yield 0.35 g.

7-Hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin.—(a) The acid (0.3 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with water (25 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) at 180-190° for 7 hours. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in faint brown coloured needles, m.p. 260-62°, mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin from resorcinol and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate was not depressed. Pechmann and Duisberg (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2127) and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 132) give m.p. 256° but Simonis and Remmert (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2231) give m.p. 262°. (b) The acid was also conveniently and quantitatively decarboxylated by heating it in a test-tube in an oil-bath at 265-270° till it melted completely and the effervescence ceased.

Methyl 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (I, R=Me; X=C₂H₅) was prepared by keeping a mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (8 g.) and purified ethyl α -ethylacetoacetate (10 g.) with sulphuric acid (80% ; 60 c.c.) for 24 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The ester crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless needles, m.p. 144-46° (Found: C, 63.6; H, 5.2. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).

The acetyl derivative, prepared by refluxing the ester with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, crystallised from dilute alcohol in clusters of tiny needles, m.p. 146-47°. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 63.2; H, 5.3 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-3-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid was obtained by keeping the ester (0.1 g.) with sodium hydroxide (5%, 10 c.c.) for 24 hours. The acid obtained on acidification was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 243-45°. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 5.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.8 per cent).

The acid was decarboxylated by heating with water in a sealed tube as before. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 196-97°, mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-

4-methylcoumarin was not depressed. Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 194-98°.

Methyl 7-hydroxy-3-propyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (I, R = Me ; X = C₂H₅).—A mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (15 g.), ethyl α -propyl-acetoacetate (15 g.) and sulphuric acid (80%, 100 c.c.) was kept for 24 hours and then added to water. The pasty mass obtained solidified partially on keeping in a frigidaire for 2 days. It was filtered, dried, washed with light petroleum ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (A). The insoluble portion was crystallised first from rectified spirit and then from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether, m.p. 133-150°. The product could not be further purified by crystallisation so the pure ester was obtained by the hydrolysis of the acetyl derivative prepared from this impure product. The acetyl derivative (0.7 g.) was shaken up with sodium hydroxide (2%, 15 c.c.) in a shaking machine for 2 hours and then kept overnight. The dissolved portion was filtered (B) and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the coumarin acid formed and the insoluble portion crystallised from rectified spirit in clusters of tiny needles, m.p. 142-44°. (Found : C, 65.1 ; H, 6.0. C₁₈H₁₆O₅ requires C, 65.2 ; H, 5.8 per cent).

The acetyl derivative, prepared as usual, was crystallised from 60% alcohol in long colourless needles, m.p. 113°. (Found : C, 64.0 ; H, 5.6. C₁₇H₁₄O₆ requires C, 64.2 ; H, 5.7 per cent).

The methyl ether, prepared as in the previous case, crystallised from 60% alcohol in small needles, m.p. 138-40°. (Found : C, 66.4 ; H, 6.4. C₁₆H₁₄O₅ requires C, 66.2 ; H, 6.2 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-3-propyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—The sodium bicarbonate solution (A) was acidified and the product obtained crystallised from rectified spirit in long colourless needles, m.p. 230-31°. (Found : C, 64.1 ; H, 5.3. C₁₆H₁₄O₅ requires C, 64.1 ; H, 5.3 per cent).

The sodium bicarbonate solution (B) gave the same acid as above, m.p. and mixed m.p. with it was the same. The acid was decarboxylated as before and the product obtained crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining needles, m.p. 171-73°, mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-3-propyl-4-methylcoumarin was the same. Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 169-71°.

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-3-butyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (I, R = Me ; X = C₄H₉).—To a mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (20 g.) and ethyl α -butyl-acetoacetate (22 g.) sulphuric acid (80%, 130 c.c.) was added gradually with shaking. After keeping for 24 hours the reaction mixture was added

to water. It was worked up as in the case of the propyl analogue and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The ester crystallised from rectified spirit in long slender needles, m.p. 163-65°. (Found : C, 66.5 ; H, 6.1. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 66.2 ; H, 6.2 per cent).

The acetyl derivative, prepared as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit in long shining needles, m.p. 111-13°. (Found : C, 65.0 ; H, 6.0. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 65.1 ; H, 6.0 per cent).

The methyl ether, prepared as usual, crystallised from dilute alcohol in light silky needles, m.p. 150-152°. (Found : C, 67.1 ; H, 6.7. $C_{17}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 67.1 ; H, 6.6 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-3-butyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—The sodium bicarbonate solution from above on acidification gave the acid which crystallised from rectified spirit in colourless shining needles, m.p. 222°. (Found: C, 65.3 ; H, 5.8. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.2 ; H, 5.8 per cent). The same acid was obtained on hydrolysis of the ester (0.3 g.) by keeping it with cold sodium hydroxide solution (20%, 15 c.c.) for 60 hours.

7-Hydroxy-3-butyl-4-methylcoumarin, obtained by decarboxylation as usual, was crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in shining plates, m.p. 134-36°. Mixed m. p. with a specimen of 7-hydroxy-3-butyl-4-methyl coumarin prepared from resorcinol (3 g.), ethyl α -butyl-acetoacetate (5.1 g.) and sulphuric acid (80%, 10 c.c.) was the same. (Found: C, 72.7 ; H, 7.3. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.4 ; H, 6.9 per cent).

Methyl 7-hydroxy-3-benzyl-4-methylcoumarin-6 carboxylate (I, R=Me; X=CH₂.C₆H₅)—To a mixture of methyl β -resorcylate (10 g.) and ethyl α -benzylacetoacetate (13.5 g.) sulphuric acid (80%, 60 c.c.) was added with shaking and after keeping for 20 hours the reaction mixture was worked up as before. The ester crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny shining needles, m.p. 186-88°. (Found: C, 70.0 ; H, 5.2. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 70.4 ; H, 4.9 per cent).

The methyl ether, prepared as usual, crystallised from rectified spirit in long colourless needles, m.p. 146-48°. (Found: C, 71.2 ; H, 5.4. $C_{20}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 71.0 ; H, 5.3 per cent).

The acetyl derivative, prepared as usual, crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny needles, m.p. 132-34°. (Found : C, 68.9 ; H, 5.0. $C_{21}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 68.9 ; H, 4.9 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-3-benzyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid was obtained by the hydrolysis of the ester (0.3 g.) by keeping it in contact with cold sodium hydroxide (10%, 30 c. c.) for 60-65 hours. It crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny needles, m.p. 247-48°. (Found: C 69.9 ; H, 4.7. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 69.7 ; H, 4.5 per cent). The same acid was also

obtained by heating the ester (0.3 g.) with sodium hydroxide solution (10% ; 25 c.c.) in a boiling water-bath for 20 minutes.

The acid was decarboxylated by heating with water in a sealed tube as usual. The product obtained crystallised from dilute alcohol in rectangular prisms, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-3-benzyl-4-methylcoumarin was 224°. Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 224°.

All the analyses recorded are micro-analyses by Dr. Schöeller.

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